

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document The Data Management Plan (DMP) provides details how all data processed, generated and produced at different modelling centres and the storage of the data, documents the data standard, provides a description of standard post-processing tools and workflow relevant software, describes data exchange with other relevant projects as well as data curation and preservation within nextGEMS. This report is a shortened version of the nextGEMS DMP that is available to all project partners.

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WP1

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1 Executive summary

This Deliverable details how all data in NextGEMS is handled and how the project addresses compliance with the FAIR data principles. Further, every work package has contributed information regarding the research data workflows applied to proceed towards the project goals. This also applies to the processing of personal data which is related to the ethics deliverable D11.1.

All information contained in this DMP is considered as preliminary and the DMP will be updated as NextGEMS progresses.

2 Conclusion & Results

In this DMP, we have detailed the approach of NextGEMS to comply with the FAIR data principles from the perspective of a project creating very large amounts of numerical model simulation output which becomes obsolete with every new step in model development. Making all data available according to the FAIR principles is technically and organisationally not possible – NextGEMS thus focuses on selected project outcomes to be made available according to the FAIR principles. All necessary information needed to handle and process data created in NextGEMS is documented in <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de> and is not contained in this DMP. That website is maintained by NextGEMS project scientists.

Further, we have collected information pertaining to project data from every work package. This information consists of contact details, data produced and reused, data dependencies between work packages, approaches to project-internal and global data-sharing and dissemination, and data archiving approaches. Due to the early stage of the NextGEMS project, all information given in this DMP is considered as preliminary and will be updated as the project progresses, i.e. the DMP is appropriately treated as a “living document”.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of NextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling ‘Earth-system’ processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth’s energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Day to day project management	yes
Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment	no
Data management	yes
Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results	no
Supporting communication and dissemination activities	yes
Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable: Data Management Plan (DMP) for NextGEMS

4.1 General project information

4.1.1 Research question of the project

NextGEMS aims to develop and apply two Storm-Resolving Earth-system Models (SR-ESMs) to the study of anthropogenic climate change. To resolve a ‘storm’, in any colloquial sense of the term, requires a grid mesh of a few km. SR-ESMs thus differ qualitatively from ‘high-resolution’ (atmosphere: 30 km) versions of traditional ESMs, in that their tenfold finer grids allows them to explicitly represent essential climate processes which even the highest resolution climate models either neglect, or parametrise. SR-ESMs are envisioned as a Flagship Activity of the World Climate Research Programme, and as the substrate for ‘Digital Twins’, one of two scientific pillars for Europe’s new initiative, ‘Destination Earth’ (Bauer et al., 2021)¹.

By developing and applying two SR-ESMs, NextGEMS will lay a new foundation for Earth-system modeling in Europe; one which will provide a new platform for advancing the frontiers of climate-change science, while also supporting Europe’s central initiative for operationalizing the Paris Agreement and realizing its envisioned ‘Green Transition’.

4.1.2 Research fields

Natural Sciences / Atmospheric Science and Oceanography

4.1.3 Keywords

storm-resolving earth system model (SR-ESM)

climate change

ICON

IFS

stakeholder involvement

science communication

4.1.4 NextGEMS coordination

The Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology, Bundesstrasse 53, D-20146 Hamburg, Germany, is the coordinating institution.

4.1.5 NextGEMS duration

Sept. 1, 2021 to Aug. 31, 2025

¹Bauer, P., Stevens, B. & Hazeleger, W. A digital twin of Earth for the green transition. Nat. Clim. Chang. 11, 80–83 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-00986-y>

4.1.6 Funder

Project funder: NextGEMS is funded through the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No - 101003470

4.1.7 NextGEMS partners

MPI-M

Full name: MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FÖRDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV, MAX-PLANCK INSTITUT FÜR METEOROLOGIE (Hamburg, Germany)

ECMWF

Full name: EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR MEDIUM-RANGE WEATHER FORECASTS

AWI

Full name: ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR UND MEERESFORSCHUNG

UiB

Full name: UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN

UCPH

Full name: KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET

CNRS

Full name: CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE

MISU

Full name: STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET

UW

Full name: UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI

UOXF

Full name: THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD

GEOMAR

Full name: HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM FÜR OZEANFORSCHUNG KIEL

BSC

Full name: BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER - CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION

BSC

Full name: BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER - CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION

BSC

Full name: BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER - CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION

UREAD

Full name: THE UNIVERSITY OF READING

WU

Full name: WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY

ETHZ

Full name: EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH

UBERN

Full name: UNIVERSITAET BERN

IPMA

Full name: INSTITUTO PORTUGUES DO MAR E DA ATMOSFERA IP

UH

Full name: HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO

UNITN

Full name: UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TRENTO

DKRZ

Full name: DEUTSCHES KLIMARECHENZENTRUM GMBH

UCM

Full name: UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID

IRD

Full name: INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT

IBE

Full name: IBERDROLA RENOVABLES ENERGIA SA

ISRA

Full name: INSTITUT SENEGALAIS DE RECHERCHES AGRICOLES

LT

Full name: LATEST THINKING GMBH

KIT

Full name: KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE

UHH

Full name: UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG

4.2 Data Summary

4.2.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of NextGEMS ?

Data production in NextGEMS primarily concerns the performance of model simulations with a multitude of models (ICON, IFS, IFS-NEMO, IFS-FESOM, FESOM, ICON-O) and model configurations (coupled, atmosphere-only, ocean-only, coarse resolution, high resolution, storm-resolving resolution). In the course of the project, the SR-ESMs will be subject to a sequence of development cycles, each of which culminates in a hackathon involving the entire NextGEMS community plus external collaborators. The hackathons work with the output data from the then current

version of the SR-ESMs, i.e. each hackathon uses a newly generated data set. At the hackathons, the model output is used to evaluate the current model performance by using available evaluation datasets in order to inform the model development tasks of the forthcoming development cycle. Further, the hackathons build the bridge to the downstream applications community by conceiving methods to inform renewable energy or fishery applications.

In the NextGEMS production phase, the SR-ESMs will produce data which will be made publicly available for general reuse through using available domain-specific and certified repositories, e.g. the World Data Center for Climate hosted at DKRZ.

Apart from the data generated for the development of the SR-ESM, other models and model setups are used to inform e.g. the design of physical parameterisations.

Another important aspect of NextGEMS is the communication concept to advertise the project goals and achievements to the general public. These efforts are supported by the generation and publication of videos - another form of data created in NextGEMS.

Survey data collected during and after the hackathons will inform a social network analysis.

Documentation facilitating the modeling and simulation workflow as well as multiple version of the project-wide data management plan will also be produced and made available to ensure efficient advancement towards the envisaged project goals.

4.2.2 What types and formats of data will be generated/collected in NextGEMS ?

Earth System Model source code.

unstandardized Earth System Model output as GRIB and/or NetCDF files (structured or unstructured depending on model).

standardized SR-ESM model output for publication and long-term reuse.

collection of observational data products from e.g. satellites or super-sites.

audiovisual data (videos).

aggregated survey data in proprietary data format, published as report/paper.

4.2.3 Do guidelines/manuals exist for a consistent organisation/handling of the data

Yes: <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>, a growing online book that documents the NextGEMS datasets, their access and usage in form of executable scripts (see details in WP2)

4.2.4 Is any existing data reused in NextGEMS ?

SR-ESM output from the DYAMOND initiative (<https://www.esiwave.eu/services/diamond-initiative>).

CMIP5 and CMIP6 data available via the ESGF or locally at DKRZ.

in-situ measurements from supersites (Cabauw, Lindenberg).

data products generated from satellite-based observations, e.g. from geostationary satellites (LandSAF products).

reanalysis datasets like ERA5.

proprietary, restricted data of IBEDROLA (IBEDROLA is an industry partner in NextGEMS).

Measurements from field campaigns, such as EUREC4A.

4.2.5 What is the expected size of the generated data?

Currently, only the anticipated data volume until the end of 2022 can be clearly estimated, because the resource allocation requests at the utilized HPC centers cover only one year.

Estimate at the state of the DMP: >2PB of SR-ESM output and supporting data, e.g. ocean spinups.

Please see details regarding the anticipated data production in the Appendix, especially WP2 and WP3.

Model source code data volume is negligible.

4.2.6 To whom might the generated data be useful ('data utility')?

The data, data products and tools produced within NextGEMS are of interest to a variety of stakeholder groups. These are

1. the global weather and climate science community
2. research communities investigating the impact of anthropogenic climate change, e.g. agriculture, fisheries or ecology
3. industry, e.g. the renewable energy sector

Furthermore, NextGEMS communication activities, e.g. the publication of videos, science explainers, storylines and policy briefs, allow for a broad dissemination of project outcomes to the general public.

4.3 Compliance with the FAIR data guiding principles

Which NextGEMS data will be made available in-line with the FAIR data principles? The FAIR data principles are applicable for data intended for long-term reuse. In highly data intensive simulation-based projects in Earth System Science such as NextGEMS, it is impractical to ensure sustained access to all produced data. The main task of NextGEMS is the development of the ICON and IFS SR-ESMs. This involves a multitude of development cycles, each of which produces several hundred TeraBytes of model output, until a final model version is obtained. Therefore, "data" produced in NextGEMS is first and foremost software. The output produced by this software is of course relevant for downstream reuse, but not the main focus of the project. Thus, the output from model development activities will not all be saved for long-term use. However, the code version, boundary conditions and general workflow procedures will be preserved in the source code repositories maintained at the modeling centers (MPI-M, ECMWF, AWI). In NextGEMS, the data made available for reuse in-line with the FAIR principles will be the following:

- selected simulation datasets in the scope of project deliverables (D2.2, D3.1 and D3.2)
- data underlying scientific publications or public project deliverables, e.g. model source code (depending on code license), analysis scripts, selected model output, selected post-processed datasets, workflow documentation
- All data produced by IFS within nextGEMS are freely and openly available.

Project data will be preserved and made available through FAIR-enabling repositories, such as the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC, suitable for model output and software), DKRZ's long-term archival service DOKU or other similar (institutional) repositories located close to the partner institutions. The WDCC is hosted at the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) - which is also a project partner in NextGEMS. Appropriate arrangements ensuring the provision of long-term archiving services are therefore in place.

Findability Publication of the simulation output in the scope of project deliverables will be performed via the WDCC (World Data Center for Climate, hosted at DKRZ). The WDCC is a CoreTrustSeal certified domain-specific repository focusing on the long-term preservation and curation of climate model output.

The archived NextGEMS data will have persistent identifiers (PIDs) in the form of Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) assigned. The DOI-assignment follows WDCC guidelines and, among others, requires supplying rich, domain specific metadata (<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/docs/CERA2MetadataSubmissionGuide.pdf>). WDCC-archived (meta)data follow domain-specific standards, e.g. CF (<https://cfconventions.org/>). WDCC-archived data is findable via the WDCC search interface (<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/ceraresearch/q>) and is also indexed in external data catalogs (e.g. Google dataset search, EUDAT B2FIND, DWD WIS-Portal). Keywords are provided and searchable. Version numbers are not provided, because every new data publication at WDCC receives a new DOI (relations to previous “versions” are documented). DKRZ staff will assist the project scientists in compiling the essential meta-data and preparing of the data to maximise long-term reusability. Publication-related data archived in DOKU are also assigned a persistent identifier and are findable via the above mentioned search interface.

Further, a list of all published and available NextGEMS data products will be maintained at the projects’ Zenodo page: <https://zenodo.org/communities/nextgems-h2020>

Accessibility As mentioned above, selected simulation output will be published via the WDCC (deliverables D2.2, D3.1 and D3.2). Data access follows WDCC-implementations, which are the use of authentication procedures (everybody is free to register for an account) and standard and open data transfer protocols. No special software is needed to access the data. Data access is free of charge.

Model source code developments will be made accessible as follows:

- ICON and ICON-ocean model source code is available from the MPI-M git repository after agreeing to a usage license (https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/iconpublic/wiki/How_to_obtain_the_model_code) and following the instructions detailed on that web page. Publication of ICON code is not possible under the current licence.
- TModel codes developed at ECMWF are the intellectual property of ECMWF and its member states, and therefore the IFS code is not publicly available. Access to a reduced version of the IFS code may be obtained from ECMWF under an OpenIFS licence (see <http://www.ecmwf.int/en/research/projects/openifs> for further information, last access: 23 March 2022). The nextGEMS IFS baseline cycle 47r3 will be available under OpenIFS in the near future.
- The FESOM ocean model is open source and available via GitHub: <https://github.com/FESOM/fesom2>. All necessary information regarding reuse and referencing of the model are documented on the FESOM projects GitHub page.

Interoperability The selected model output made available via the WDCC will be prepared in accordance with domain-specific (meta)data standards, such as the CF or CMIP naming conventions. This is a prerequisite of data preservation in WDCC. The file format will be netCDF or GRIB/GRIB2, which are both open, and in the case of netCDF self-describing, file formats being the de-facto standard in simulation-based climate science. NetCDF and GRIB/GRIB2 data are accessible and processable by any software making use of the netCDF and/or GRIB libraries, e.g. python, R, Julia, NCL or CDOs. If (meta)data naming does, for any reason, not comply with any of the above standards, mapping tables are provided at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/>. In WDCC, the data will be available as structured global arrays with standardised coordinate variables. This allows for combination with any dataset available on a structured and geo-referenced grid.

Reusability The model simulation output published via the WDCC in the scope of project deliverables D2.2, D3.1 and D3.2 will be made available under the CC-BY 4.0 license. Further, these data are supplied with rich domain-specific metadata facilitating reuse.

Model source code developments are reusable following the licensing frameworks of the individual institutions:

- MPI-M: https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/iconpublic/wiki/How_to_obtain_the_model_code
- AWI: FESOM open source code available via GitHub (<https://github.com/FESOM/fesom2>) References are given on the GitHub page
- ECMWF: Research access to IFS code is facilitated through the freely available OpenIFS licence and ECMWF makes available an increasing number of code modules under an open-source compatible licence. The nextGEMS baseline cycle 47r3 will be available under OpenIFS in the near future.

4.4 Resources

4.4.1 Required IT resources

The following IT-resources needed for the successful conductance of NextGEMS are as follows:

- required IT resources at DKRZ have been applied for.
- required IT resources at an HPC facility other than DKRZ have been applied for.

Status of the application for IT-resources:

DKRZ resources: the following resources at DKRZ for 2022 were requested in the application round at the end of 2021:

- compute: 1 572 000 node hours
- disk storage: 1025 TB
- /arch/ storage: 1625 TB
- long-term archive (DOKU): 0

Of this request, the following amounts were granted:

- compute: 943 200 node hours
- disk storage: 718 TB
- /arch/ storage: 1625 TB
- long-term archive (DOKU): 0

Additional to the resources requested at DKRZ, NextGEMS also applied for compute resources at Jülich Supercomputing Center for performing NextGEMS simulations on JEWELS-BOOSTER. The request was granted. See details of WP2 for more details or check the [online reference to approved PRACE grants](#). Resources for the upcoming years of NextGEMS will be applied for in the framework of the common HPC resource application cycles.

4.4.2 Required resources for making data FAIR

No additional resources apart from those supplied by the funder (6PM funding) are required for making the NextGEMS data FAIR. Long-term preservation of data in e.g. the WDCC is free of charge. Domain-specific advice on data preparation is a general DKRZ service available to the entire German climate science community, hence also NextGEMS.

4.4.3 Who will be responsible for RDM aspects in NextGEMS ?

The responsibility of generating the NextGEMS data management plan is with DKRZ. This DMP lists data responsible persons per work package in the respective sections in the Appendix.

4.5 Data security

4.5.1 What provisions are in place for data security?

The model source code developments are performed using automatically backed-up repositories such as GitHub. The GitHub instance used to develop the ICON model is hosted at DKRZ. The FESOM git-repository is hosted on the general GitHub instance. Model output is stored on hard-disk or on tape. In case of hardware failure, the data can be recomputed.

It is in the responsibility of individual NextGEMS scientists to ensure the safety of their personal analysis routines and results by employing good data management practice in their day-to-day workflow, such as ensuring that essential methodological and analytical information is stored in automatically backed-up sections of the used infrastructure. E.g., the \$HOME directories of every user at DKRZ supply ample storage space and are backed-up daily.

Access to the HPC systems where the model output data are stored is restricted to accredited users of the respective HPC infrastructure. If desired, access to the NextGEMS data can be restricted to project members. This is however not anticipated, as the expected interest in the generated data spans a multitude of different user groups.

4.5.2 Reproducibility of the data produced in NextGEMS

Climate model simulation output can be reproduced given the workflows used to create particular output sets are preserved.

Model source code is maintained in institutional and backed-up code repositories. Unless these repositories don't fail, model source code is reproducible.

Post-processed data products can be reproduced given that workflow reproducibility is ensured.

Observational products used for analysis can be obtained from third-party data holdings, as NextGEMS itself does not produce observational data products.

4.5.3 Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

NextGEMS data selected for long-term archival, preservation and curation will be stored in domain-specific and certified repositories such as WDCC or PANGAEA. Project data underlying scientific publications and or which is required as a documentation of project progress will be long-term archived using high-quality institutional services such as DKRZ's DOKU or KITs RADAR4KIT services.

4.6 Partner institutions

4.7 Work package specific data management

4.7.1 Work package WP1 Coordination

Overarching goals of WP1 Coordination

The overall objective of the Management Work Package is to ensure an effective implementation of the project, to deliver high-quality work standards and innovation actions, and to implement successful collaboration in different settings. The major activities comprise

- Day to day project management.
- Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment (Critical Risks).

- Data management.
- Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results.
- Supporting communication and dissemination activities.
- Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes.

Data categories produced in WP1 Coordination

other: Data Management Plan, web page, project organisation data

Specific datasets produced in WP1 Coordination

Data Management Plan.

Web page(s): <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>.

project internal and personal data of project scientists.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP1 Coordination focus on

not applicable to this WP

Is input from other NextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP1 Coordination ?

Yes

Every WP

As early as possible

Does work in WP1 Coordination depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP1 Coordination ?

less than 1TB.

Measures taken in WP1 Coordination to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of NextGEMS :

not applicable to this WP.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP1 Coordination be performed?

yes, of selected data: DMP content is daily backed-up (<https://rdmo.dkrz.de>), web content backups as performed by the provider); project/personal data stored/backed-up by GWDG cloud service (owncloud) and external hard disk.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP1 Coordination ?

RDMO: DKRZ data management (cron job runs daily).

Web content: provider of web resources.

Project/personal data: GWDG and NextGEMS project office (Theresa Mieslinger, Heike Konow).

NextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP1 Coordination :

NextGEMS DMP: project-internal communication of data-related aspects.

NextGEMS Webpages: communication and dissemination, orientation for project scientists.

project/personal data: project coordination.

Organization of NextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP1 Coordination :

The NextGEMS DMP is made available via the NextGEMS cloud store. Further, public releases will be openly released according to EU guidelines for Open Research Data Pilots.

Will data produced in WP1 Coordination be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: administrative project data.

Yes, externally for everyone: DMP (public deliverable), website.

No: personal data.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP1 Coordination be published or shared?

Data Management Plan (DMP): the NextGEMS DMP will be made available via the channels made foreseen by the EU.

Website: openly accessible.

When will the data produced in WP1 Coordination be published or shared?

in accordance with project planning of deliverables.

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information of the data produced in WP1 Coordination ?

DMP: DKRZ

project/personal data: nextGEMS project office.

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP1 Coordination be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Has not yet been decided.

Who is responsible for the archival of data produced in WP1 Coordination ?

DKRZ

4.7.2 Work package WP2 Model Development

Overarching goals of WP2 Model Development

- To perform the Cycle 2 and initiate the Cycle 3 simulations of the Development Phase.
- To address errors and fine-tune the SR-ESMs, including associated output and data management strategies, based on feedback from, and together with, the S&R, S&O, S&L themes.
- To implement selected applications in SR-ESMs in collaboration with the four themes and users.
- To organise scrums to address data management and data analysis workflows in support of Hackathons and simulations analysis within NextGEMS and beyond.

Data categories produced in WP2 Model Development

climate model output: ECMWF: IFS-FESOM2, MPI-M: ICON-ESM.

software/tool: ICON, IFS, FESOM, NEMO.

other: project-wide data documentation wiki/homepage: <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>.

Specific datasets produced in WP2 Model Development

ECMWF: IFS-FESOM for NextGEMS Cycle 2 (IFS TCo2559 (4.5 km) coupled to FESOM2 (8 km) for 6-12 months), IFS TCo3999 (2.8 km) coupled to FESOM2 (4 km) for two selected seasons (e.g. winter and summer).

MPI-M: ICON-ESM for NextGEMS Cycle 2: ICON (5 km, coupled) for 1-2 years, ICON (5 km, coupled) for 3 months.

ECMWF @JSC: IFS-FESOM, 2.8km atmosphere, 4 km ocean, 6 months AND 2 or 4 years in length.

ECMWF: simulations mirroring the above (IFS@8km with FESOM2).

MPI-M: simulations mirroring the above (ICON @10km).

MPI-M@JSC: ICON-ICON ocean, 2.5km atmosphere, 2.5 or 5km ocean, 6 months AND 2 or 4 years in length.

DKRZ: DKRZ will establish and maintain, with the input from project scientists, the simulation and analysis wiki maintained at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de> (see also Deliverable D2.1). This resource will form the central information portal regarding usability and accessibility of NextGEMS simulation output at the project-level. This information is essential for the successful conductance of NextGEMS Hackathons.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP2 Model Development focus on

ECMWF, MPI-M: IFS-FESOM2 and ICON output for Cycle 2 simulations will be informed by the experiences from the first NextGEMS hackathon. Output is documented at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/>

ECMWF, MPI-M: IFS-FESOM2 and ICON output for Cycle 3 simulations is tbd.

Is input from other NextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP2 Model Development ?

Yes

WP6: ocean spinup

as soon as possible

Does work in WP2 Model Development depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP2 Model Development ?

more than 1PB: JSC: >600TB (IFS and ICON), DKRZ: ICON 1,025 PB, ECMWF: IFS up to 500 TB.

Measures taken in WP2 Model Development to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of NextGEMS :

reduction of model output volume, e.g. compression, reduction of output frequency and/or variables (please specify shortly): set of output variables adapted to the findings of the first hackathon.

automated transfer to tape archive during model runtime, incl. appropriate documentation and/or metadata capture.

deletion of superfluous data.

transfer of not frequently used datasets to tape archive.

other: transfer of data from JSC to DKRZ.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP2 Model Development be performed?

yes, of model/tool source code.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP2 Model Development ?

ECMWF model development team

ICON model development team

FESOM model development team

NextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP2 Model Development :

SR-ESM output produced in WP2 forms the basis for successful NextGEMS hackathons. NextGEMS hackathons

focus on fine-tuning and preparing the models for production runs.

NextGEMS analysis wiki will provide the central reference document for all project-internal simulation data access, processing and evaluation methods.

Model source code developments will be used to perform simulations and result in SR-ESMs ready for NextGEMS production runs to inform the projects' Application phase.

Organization of NextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP2 Model Development :

The current state, availability, format and content of SR-ESM output is documented at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>. This web instance is maintained by DKRZ and critically relies on timely and accurate input of project scientists in order to serve the intended purpose.

The data of NextGEMS Cycle2 and Cycle3 simulations is/will be made available at DKRZ.

Each model development cycle of NextGEMS culminates in a Hackathon at which the output of the corresponding simulations (Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 simulations) is analysed. The findings inform the next development cycle.

ECMWF: Cycle 2 simulations with IFS-FESOM2 will be performed at Juwels. Data needs to be copied to DKRZ, similar to the strategy for ICON that we will adopt. Simulations are to be started early this year. Format is expected to be similar if not identical to Cycle 1 IFS output. The data is made available to everyone at the DKRZ supercomputer, as was done for the Cycle 1 simulations analyzed during the first Hackathon.

MPI-M: Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 simulations are performed at DKRZ and at JSC. The data produced at JSC will have to be transferred to DKRZ to make it available for analysis. This is also necessary because storage quotas at JSC are comparatively small (ca 100TB in total).

DKRZ: provision of an accurate and up-to-date NextGEMS analysis wiki critically depends on timely and precise input from the modeller providing the output data.

Will data produced in WP2 Model Development be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 model output needed for the hackathons; model source code.

Yes, externally for everyone: simulation output published via deliverables D2.2.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP2 Model Development be published or shared?

D2.2 Release (publishing in the sense of DOI provision) of selected Cycle 2 Simulations. (Task 2.2) (M14, MPI-M) (publication in WDCC with DOI), exact amount and content of published data is tbd.

D2.1 analysis wiki is accessible for interested outside users, as it is an openly accessible web page (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>).

Model source code is available via institutional repositories following the respective licensing agreements (see Sec. 3).

When will the data produced in WP2 Model Development be published or shared?

Publication of data (standardised simulation output) will happen according to the timeline defined by the deliverables laid out in the project grand agreement; primary data underlying scientific publications will be published according to FAIR data principles at the time required by the publisher.

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information of the data produced in WP2 Model Development ?

MPI-M and ECMWF

not applicable to DKRZ task of supplying the analysis wiki

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP2 Model Development be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Discipline specific data center: WDCC

Other: DKRZ web-server (analysis wiki), GitHub (model source code)

Who is responsible for the archival of data produced in WP2 Model Development ?

MPI-M and ECMWF

4.7.3 Work package WP3 Production

Overarching goals of WP3 Production

- To complete Cycle 3 (Development) simulations.
- To finalize the configuration (including associated output and data management requirements) of SR-ESMs for the production simulations.
- To finalize the configuration (including associated output and data management requirements) of SR-ESMs for the production simulations.
- To perform present day and future projections (i.e., production simulations).
- To organize and curate simulation output for sustainable access beyond the completion of NextGEMS.
- To support the four themes in exploring extensions of SR-ESMs to address additional application needs and testing proposed model improvements.

Data categories produced in WP3 Production

climate model output: IFS and ICON SR-ESMs in final configuration.

Specific datasets produced in WP3 Production

Two (ICON and IFS) climate projections for the period between 2020-2049 with a target horizontal resolution of 2 km to 3 km.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP3 Production focus on

The exact content and scope of production runs is tbd.

Is input from other NextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP3 Production ?

Yes

WP2, model development. Production runs in WP3 can only be conducted if work on the SR-ESMs progresses as planned.

M24 (as given by the project plan in the grant agreement).

Does work in WP3 Production depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP3 Production ?

100TB to 1PB: no concrete estimate available yet.

Measures taken in WP3 Production to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of NextGEMS :

reduction of model output volume, e.g. compression, reduction of output frequency and/or variables (please specify shortly): tbd

automated transfer to tape archive during model runtime, incl. appropriate documentation and/or metadata capture.

deletion of superfluous data.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP3 Production be performed?

yes, of model/tool source code.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP3 Production ?

AWI, MPI-M, and ECMWF

NextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP3 Production :

The initiation and use of the production simulations and their output are identified the Application Phase of NextGEMS.

Climate change experiments at unprecedented SR resolution will be applied in new avenues of climate change impact research.

Future directions of SR-ESM developments will be identified.

Results from analysis of production simulations inform the modeling path towards DestinE.

Organization of NextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP3 Production :

The exact technical and organisational setting of collaboration on the large-volume output of the production simulations is still to be determined. Similar to the data organisation for the hackathons in development cycles 2 and 3, the bulk of NextGEMS data will be available at DKRZ (either on disk or tape). Data workflows developed until then (in cooperation with other funded projects, e.g. WarmWorld or ACROSS) will most probably facilitate data access and processing.

Will data produced in WP3 Production be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: simulation output from production runs needed for project-internal assessment and tool-development.

Yes, externally for everyone: simulation output as specified in deliverables D3.1 and D3.2.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP3 Production be published or shared?

Data underlying scientific publications will be made available following the FAIR data principles by e.g. making use of DKRZ's WDCC and/or DOKU long-term archiving services, other similar long-term archiving services close to partner institutions and institutional code repositories.

D3.1 Release (publishing in the sense of DOI provision) of Cycle 3 Simulations. (Task 3.1) (M22, AWI) (WDCC publication with DOI).

D3.2 Release (publishing in the sense of DOI provision) of production simulations. (Task 3.2) (M30, MPIM) (WDCC publication with DOI).

When will the data produced in WP3 Production be published or shared?

Publication of paper(s) or see timeline given in the NextGEMS grant agreement.

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information of the data produced in WP3 Production ?

MPI-M and ECMWF

DKRZ long-term archival support staff

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP3 Production be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Own institution

Discipline specific data center: WDCC

Who is responsible for the archival of data produced in WP3 Production ?

MPI-M and ECMWF

4.7.4 Work package WP4/5 Storms & Radiation

Overarching goals of WP4/5 Storms & Radiation

- To stabilize the climate of next-generation models by balancing top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation and implement a simplified aerosol scheme, in order to enable studies of Earth's climate sensitivity and aerosol forcing in the Application phase (WP5).
- To identify shortcomings related to remaining sub-grid scale processes, including representation of turbulent transport and mixing, cloud microphysics and subgrid cloud structures.
- To implement online diagnostics of wind energy potential in an innovative bi-directional endeavour, jointly with stakeholders, in order to prepare an assessment of the impacts of changing emissions of CO₂ and aerosols on efforts to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy in the Application phase.
- To test hypotheses, and quantify processes related to aerosols, clouds and their influences on climate change with a new degree of precision and fidelity.
- To develop parametrisations of cloud micro-physics and mixing, and apply advanced data-assimilation methods to model tuning.
- To advance science and support efforts to operationalise the Paris agreement to limit global warming, through improved assessments of aerosol forcing, radiative feedbacks and climate sensitivity.
- To exploit the online diagnostics implemented in the Development phase to investigate the impact of a changing climate on solar and wind energy production in a joint hackathon.

Data categories produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation

climate model output: MISU: ICON atmosphere only, UOXF: ICON-HAM CRM setup.

other model output: UOXF: HAM output, LES.

software/tool: diagnostic code, ICON source code.

Specific datasets produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation

MISU: Wind and solar power diagnostic code, will be developed at and around hackathon 2.

MISU: ICON atmosphere-only simulations to look at feedbacks, forcing and pattern effects.

UOXF: Development of reduced complexity aerosol model HAM, and its implementation in ICON will produce offline and implementation simulation data, from regional to global configuration Later, production of perturbed aerosol runs with ICON.

KIT: ICON model output, dust emissions, and dust-storm simulation.

LES in support of sub-gridscale parameterizations.

UOXF: ICON-HAM CRM setup, 20-30 runs, 1km resolution, 1000x2000km² domain.

UW: tbd

CNRS: tbd

UH: tbd

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation focus on

Standard ICON model output.

TBD, as it is not clear at this time which parameters are needed and which will be omitted from model output routines.

Is input from other NextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation ?

Yes

ICON and IFS NextGEMS model runs, prepared for hackathons by MPI and ECMWF (WP2).

Current status of model source code, model configurations, model initial and boundary conditions (WP2).

as soon as the WP2 simulations and model source code developments are ready for project use.

Does work in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation depend on external data sources?

Yes

Observational data sets for evaluation, eg EUREC4A.

KIT: These data likely includes observational data, such as satellite or ground-based remote sensing data, existing model simulations from project partners or external sources (e.g. DWD).

KIT: Further, own (re-)used data might include existing source code for model development, or postprocessing and analysis, as well as already processed/manipulated data from external sources.

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation ?

100TB to 1PB: exact amount tbd

Measures taken in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of NextGEMS :

Not specified yet, but needed

Will regular backups of data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be performed?

yes, of model/tool source code

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation ?

see "data responsables"

NextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation :

Analysis of atmosphere-only simulations to look at feedbacks, forcing and pattern effects.

Development of reduced complexity aerosol model based on HAM and its implementation in ICON.

Development of subgrid-scale parameterizations.

Computation of wind and solar diagnostics for use by the renewable energy sector.

Organization of NextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation :

MISU: We would do our best to share data to project partners, but the method will depend on what, how much and on which time scale. When handling large amounts of data there is no single best solution. There is no long term storage options on LUMI, data will need to be moved elsewhere.

UOXF: Simulations are only partly conducted at DKRZ. The process of making data available to project partners (in case this is desired) still has to be sorted out.

KIT: Depending on the HPC system used (e.g. at DKRZ or at KIT), data will be stored at DKRZ or at the Large Scale Data Facility (LSDF) at KIT. In the case that data will be stored at KIT, download of data or remote access to the data sets via THREDDS data server (TDS) or S3 object storage can be provided. Depending on which system is used, there are different protocols to work with the data sets via remote access frameworks (OpeNDAP, CSW, URL etc.). While this tools cover data sharing during ongoing working processes repositories like Radar4KIT (<https://radar.kit.edu>), Pangaea (<https://www.pangaea.de>) or WDCC (<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/>) can be used to share and cite final data sets. Regardless of which system is used, sharing communities should be defined if the data won't be open source. Those sharing communities will build the basis to define access rights.

Will data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: model source code developments, intermediate evaluation results, diagnostic code.

Yes, externally for everyone: project data underlying scientific publications.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be published or shared?

WDCC/DOKU @DKRZ (<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/ceraresearch/info?site=submitinfo>)

Radar4KIT (<https://radar.kit.edu>)

Pangaea (<https://www.pangaea.de>)

Data underlying scientific publications will be made available following the FAIR data principles by e.g. making use of DKRZ's WDCC and/or DOKU long-term archiving services, other similar long-term archiving services close to partner institutions and institutional code repositories.

When will the data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be published or shared?

Publication of paper(s) or see timeline given in the NextGEMS grant agreement.

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information of the data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation ?

tbd

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Discipline specific data center: WDCC, PANGAEA

Generic data center: RADAR4KIT

Who is responsible for the archival of data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation ?

KIT, MISU, and UOXF

4.7.5 Work package WP6/7 Storms & Ocean

Overarching goals of WP6/7 Storms & Ocean

- To identify and evaluate key ocean and marine atmosphere features in the SR-ESM simulations of all three development cycles.
- To validate the marine planetary boundary layer representation of the SR-ESM simulations.
- To provide ocean initial conditions for the coupled SR-ESM simulations.
- To provide developments towards an ocean mixed layer scheme adequate for SR-ESMs.
- To create numerical tools that generate output streams useful to the planetary boundary layer, ocean mixed-layer and fisheries communities.
- To identify the importance of meso-scale air-sea interaction on tropical climate, on its dominant patterns of variability and teleconnections, and on its response to global warming • To appraise the significance of resolving atmospheric convection and storm-scales for simulating the West African Monsoon (WAM) and hydrological cycle extremes, and their response to global warming.
- To evaluate the influence of mesoscales on tropical cyclones and on their response to global warming.
- To assess the impacts of climate and climate change on global primary productivity, and global and West African fisheries using SR-ESMs.
- To anticipate the relevance of resolving mesoscale circulations for global climate change assessments.
- To evaluate and refine new ocean mixed layer and planetary boundary layer representation in the coupled system.

Data categories produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean

other model output: ICON-O, FESOM2

model-data evaluation products: UCM: model evaluation based on observational datasets

other: observations database

Specific datasets produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean

GEOMAR, NBI: In situ observation of large mixing events in the tropical mixed layer.

MPI-M: ICON-O stand-alone simulations at r2b8 (10km) and ocean spin-up simulations at r2b9 (5km) resolution.

MPI-M: ICON-O sensitivity experiments (r2b8), 3-5 experiments of 5-10 years length.

AWI: stand-alone FESOM2 simulations forced by ERA5; 3-5 experiments of 5-10 years length.

AWI: stand-alone, ERA5 forced spin-up simulation at NG5 resolution, 10 years long.

AWI: stand-alone, ERA5 forced spin-up at Rossby 4.1 resolution for the final IFS/FESOM simulations.

UCM: model evaluation analysis.

UUREAD, IRD, ISRA: to be determined.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean focus on

GEOMAR, NBI: parameters relevant to ocean mixing.

MPI-M: ICON-O output and output necessary for ESM coupling (spin-up simulations).

AWI: FESOM output and output necessary for ESM coupling (spin-up simulations).

Is input from other NextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean ?

Yes

GEOMAR, NBI: no.

AWI, MPI-M: maybe, depends on suitability of simulations produced for the individual NextGEMS cycles.

UCM: Data from simulations (WP2) whenever available.

Whenever available, at least in the framework of NextGEMS Hackathons.

Does work in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean depend on external data sources?

Yes

GEOMAR, NBI: observational data products.

MPI-M, AWI: ERA5 reanalysis data (available at DKRZ).

UCM: Observation and reanalysis data to compare with simulations (ERA5, GPCP, CRU, CMAP, CPC, HadISST, ERSST, OISST, ORAS5, SODA342).

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean ?

100TB to 1PB: ca 150 TB (MPI-M and AWI ocean runs).

Measures taken in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of NextGEMS :

automated transfer to tape archive during model runtime, incl. appropriate documentation and/or metadata capture.

transfer of not frequently used datasets to tape archive.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be performed?

yes, of all relevant data.

yes, of model/tool source code.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean ?

see "data responsables"

NextGEMS-internal use of data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean :

GEOMAR: Model evaluation (ocean).

MPI-M and AWI: stand-alone model simulations are used to test parameterisations.

MPI-M and AWI: spin-up simulations will be used by WP2 and WP3 to perform the coupled SR-ESM simulations.

Organization of NextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean :

GEOMAR, NBI: data will be shared with project partners during the course of the project. Technical realisation to be determined.

MPI-M and AWI: stand-alone ocean simulations are performed at DKRZ and will be made available to all project partners. **UCM:** results from model evaluation will be fed back to the model development WPs **UREAD, IRD:** to be determined

Will data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: ocean spin-up as basis for Cycle2, 3 and production simulations; ocean model evaluation results.

Yes, externally for everyone: project data underlying scientific publications.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be published or shared?

Data underlying scientific publications will be made available following the FAIR data principles by e.g. making use of DKRZ's WDCC and/or DOKU long-term archiving services and institutional code repositories.

More specific: Selected datasets (e.g. sensitivity experiments used for publications) will be available to the general community using suitable infrastructure available.

When will the data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be published or shared?

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information of the data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean ?

see "data responsables"

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Discipline specific data center: PANGAEA, WDCC.

Has not yet been decided.

Who is responsible for the archival of data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean ?

see "data responsables"

4.7.6 Work package WP8/9 Storms & Land

Overarching goals of WP8/9 Storms & Land

- Evaluate surface energy, water and momentum balance components as well as near-surface meteorology

over land at storm-resolving resolution against observations and coarser resolution simulations.

- Represent land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolution by making use of the latest generation remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation.
- Prepare the NextGEMS models to best serve the science and applications, by implementing online output statistics co-developed with stakeholders, with a pilot project focusing on solar energy.
- Expand scope of the SR-ESM by coupling it offline to a terrestrial biosphere model.
- Investigate whether resolving the storm-scale variability in weather systems and in the land surface, together with their consistent interactions with the larger scales, affects the climatology of blocking, the statistics of dry and warm spells, the mean surface radiation balance as well as near-term changes in aggregated temperature and precipitation statistics.
- Quantify the carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe at storm-resolving resolution and compare these estimates to ones from current ESMs.
- Use the production runs to reassess solar power on the global scale and to produce global maps of hazardous weather at unprecedented resolution.

Data categories produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land

model-data evaluation products: IPMA: land surface temperature from satellite observations; WU: model evaluation with supersite data at specific locations.

Specific datasets produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land

IPMA: monthly and seasonal mean diurnal cycles of land surface temperature derived from geostationary satellite observations.

WU: outcomes of model evaluation against supersite data.

MPIM, UBERN, ETHZ: to be determined.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land focus on

IPMA: land surface temperature (derived from satellite observations).

Is input from other NextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP8/9 Storms & Land ?

Yes

IPMA, WU: IFS and ICON simulations produced in WP2.

IPMA, WU: throughout the project.

Does work in WP8/9 Storms & Land depend on external data sources?

Yes

IPMA: MSG geostationary land surface temperatures produced in the framework of LandSAF. Further information: <https://landsaf.ipma.pt/en/products/land-surface-temperature/1st/>.

WU: data from observational sites, including the CESAR observatory in Cabauw, The Netherlands, the Lindenberg Observatory for the evaluation of the models in WP8 and the further analysis of the data in WP9. This is throughout the final three years of the project. The Cabauw data is available at <https://ruisdael-observatory.nl/cesar/>. Lindenberg data is available throughout the DWD website.

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land ?

1TB to 100TB: IPMA: 2.2TB (original LandSAF data).

Measures taken in WP8/9 Storms & Land to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of NextGEMS :

not applicable to this WP.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be performed?

yes, of model/tool source code.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP8/9 Storms & Land ?

IPMA and WU

NextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land :

IPMA: monthly and seasonal mean diurnal cycles of land surface temperature produced in this WP will be used to evaluate model simulations.

WU: analysis of data from ICON and IFS and comparison against station data at location to be determined (see supersite data which is planned to be used).

MPIM: to be determined

Organization of NextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land :

IPMA: since the original data is freely available, the processed data can be also made available to the project partners and/or general community. But for that we would need to have a data repository.

WU: Processed data will be freely available to other researchers.

Will data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: compiled datasets used for model evaluation; model evaluation results.

Yes, externally for everyone: project data underlying scientific publications.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be published or shared?

Data underlying scientific publications will be made available following the FAIR data principles by e.g. making use of DKRZ's WDCC and/or DOKU long-term archiving services and institutional code repositories.

WU: Data from observational sites will follow the data policy of the respective stations. Processed data by our work package will be freely available to other researchers.

IPMA: since the original data is freely available, the processed data can be also made available to the project partners and/or general community. But for that we would need to have a data repository.

When will the data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be published or shared?

Publication of paper(s) or see timeline given in the NextGEMS grant agreement.

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information of the data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land ?

IPMA and WU

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Own institution.

Discipline specific data center: WDCC, PANGAEA.

Who is responsible for the archival of data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land ?

IPMA, in collaboration with repository staff, and WU

4.7.7 Work package WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication

Overarching goals of WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication

- Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS coproduction, communication & dissemination and video presence.
- Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process).
- Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination).
- Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination).

Data categories produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication

other: Storylines, research videos (vlog), survey data.

Specific datasets produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication

Outreach and Communication Videos.

Survey among hackathon participants as basis for social network analysis.

Storylines.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication focus on

not applicable to this WP.

Is input from other NextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication ?

Yes.

Input from all project participants is needed to create the envisaged data products.

Throughout the project.

Does work in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication ?

less than 1TB

Measures taken in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of NextGEMS :

not applicable to this WP.

transfer of not frequently used datasets to tape archive.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be performed?

yes, of all relevant data.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication ?

BSC and LT

NextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication :

BSC: The collected data will be analysed using social network analysis.

WP10 will, in collaboration with other project themes and users, develop storylines. At least two storylines will be developed. The storyline on renewable energy will depend on data produced in WP5, as well as the knowledge coproduced in collaboration with project partners and users from the renewable energy sector. The deadline for the final storyline is M46, but we expect an earlier version by M36 so that the results can be shared and finetuned with other users. The storyline on fisheries and food security in Western Africa will depend on data produced in WP7 and the knowledge coproduced with the project partner and users from fisheries, as well as policy makers. The final deadline for this storyline is M46, but an early draft should be available by M36, so that results can be presented in workshops and other events to the broader user and policy community.

LT: produced videos will display and communicate the project goals and progress as well as scientist portraits in the framework of a Vlog.

Organization of NextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication :

BSC: Survey data about the relationships between hackathon participants will be collected at each hackathon. Results of the social network analysis will be made available via reports or papers.

LT: videos are created in conjunction with the NextGEMS scientists and are embedded into the projects' homepage.

Will data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: intermediate results of social network analysis.

Yes, externally for everyone: report/publication using anonymised data from the social network analysis, videos, science explainers, communication material.

No: raw data from social network analysis

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be published or shared?

BSC: The results of the social network analysis will be publicly available, either through reports or through research papers. All data will be anonymized and presented in an aggregated form.

LT: videos will be published via the NextGEMS homepage: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/> and are hosted via LT's Vimeo account: <https://vimeo.com/latestthinking>.

When will the data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be published or shared?

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information of the data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication ?

BSC and LT

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Has not yet been decided

Who is responsible for the archival of data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction,

Dissemination & Communication ?

see "data responsables"

4.7.8 Work package WP11 Ethics requirements

Overarching goals of WP11 Ethics requirements

This work package sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.

other: Protection of personal data (POPD) guidelines

Specific datasets produced in WP11 Ethics requirements

POPD - requirement No. 3

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP11 Ethics requirements focus on

not applicable to this WP.

Is input from other NextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP11 Ethics requirements ?

No

n/a

Does work in WP11 Ethics requirements depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements ?

less than 1TB

Measures taken in WP11 Ethics requirements to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of NextGEMS :

not applicable to this WP.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be performed?

yes, of all relevant data.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP11 Ethics requirements ?

Project Office, GWDG cloud service provider.

NextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements :

This work package sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.

Organization of NextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements :

Available to project members via the projects' cloud storage (contact the project office for more information).

Will data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: POPD document (deliverable D11.1).

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be published or shared?

GWDG cloud service

When will the data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be published or shared?

According to deliverable publication defined in grant agreement (M3 of the project).

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information of the data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements ?

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Has not yet been decided.

Who is responsible for the archival of data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements ?

5 References (Bibliography)

References are provided as footnotes in the above text.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
x	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This report will be made public via the project website. The DMP is accessible to project partners via the internal file distribution.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes. The delay was approved by our project's EC coordinator.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

No changes.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

Links were built with all other WPs of NextGEMS in order to collect the information contained in this DMP.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon, 19.10. - 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- NextGEMS Office Hour to introduce the DMP and its concept (13 Jan 2022)

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.